

The Availability of the Focus Standards on Human Resources and Processes as a Potential for Excellence in Palestinian Universities According to the European Model

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Abstract: The study aimed to identify the availability of the two focus criteria on human resources and processes as a means of excellence in Palestinian universities according to the European model in the Palestinian universities. The study used the analytical descriptive method. The study was conducted on the university leadership in Al-Azhar and Islamic Universities. The study sample consisted of (135) individuals, (119) of whom responded, and the questionnaire was used in collecting data. The results of the study were as follows: (a) High level of achievement of the criterion of focus on human resources with a percentage of (73.6%). The sub-areas of the HR focus were as follows: (reward, appreciation and attention to human resources at the university, Identify and develop the continuity of knowledge and qualifications of human resources, and finally: planning, management and development of human resources). There is a high standard of emphasis on operations with a percentage of (74.6%). The sub-areas of the Process Focus Standard are as follows: (Process Design and Management Methodology, Process Improvement in Creative Ways to Generate Value Added for Students and Beneficiaries, Design and Development of Academic Programs and Internal Services by Students' need). The study presented a number of recommendations, the most important of which are: Making more efforts in the planning, management and development of human resources in universities, working to identify and develop the continuity of knowledge and qualifications of human resources through training courses and scholarships for the members of the academic body, working to increase the participation and empowerment of human resources in decision making, and work on the design and development of academic programs and internal services according to the needs of students and to meet the labor market.

Keywords: Human Resources, Operations Standard, Excellence, European Model, Palestinian Universities.

1. INTRODUCTION

The organizations in various fields, including universities in our era - the era of globalization and knowledge - to implement TQM to achieve excellence in performance, and to achieve a competitive advantage by completing the process of accreditation of local quality bodies to obtain international certificates of excellence, International (El Talla et al., 2018).

Several institutions have applied some of the strategic performance measurement models, and others have sought to implement excellence models as tools for evaluating performance and improving organizational performance (Jad Al-Rab, 2013).

The European model emphasizes that excellence in performance, serving beneficiaries and achieving benefits for stakeholders and society at large is achieved through leadership that shapes strategies and policies, directs human resources, invests relationships and optimally manages various processes in the organization (El Talla et al., 2018).

Despite the interest of many researchers in the study of the approach of excellence, there is a relative scarcity, especially

in studies that examined the criterion of human resources and processes as a potential for excellence, and is one of the topics worthy of research at length and with great care of researchers, because of increased competition, Customer expectations, which ultimately affect performance improvement (El Talla et al., 2018) point out that the most important high performance factors come from the organization itself before the ocean and rather from its resources.

Based on the above, the current study is considered one of the rare studies aimed at answering the following main question:

What are the criteria for focusing on human resources and processes as a means of excellence in Palestinian universities according to the European model?

It has the following sub-questions:

Q1-: What is the availability of the focus on human resources in Palestinian public universities operating in the southern governorates?

Q2-: What is the availability of the standard of operations in the Palestinian public universities operating in the southern governorates?

2. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

In line with the study's questions, the current study seeks to achieve a set of objectives, namely:

1. To disclose the availability of the standard of focus on human resources in the Palestinian public universities operating in the southern governorates.
2. To clarify the availability of the standard of operations in the Palestinian public universities operating in the southern governorates.

3. RESEARCH IMPORTANCE

1. Providing the Palestinian universities with the availability of the human resources standard as one of the possibilities of excellence for the European model.
2. Providing the Palestinian universities with the availability of the standard of operations as one of the possibilities of excellence for the European model.
3. To provide recommendations and proposals documented and derived from the field study to help senior management of Palestinian universities in applying the possibilities of the European model of excellence.
4. This study may contribute to drawing the attention of researchers to carry out many studies and researches in modern administrative curricula and apply them to a vital sector such as the higher education sector.
5. The lack of adequate field studies focused on the availability of the European model of excellence in Palestinian universities in particular.

4. RESEARCH LIMITS AND SCOPE

1. **Objective Limit:** The study was limited to identifying the availability of the two standards of focus on human resources and processes as a means of excellence in Palestinian universities according to the European model.
2. **Human Limit:** This study is limited to the responses of administrative staff.
3. **Institutional limitation:** The study was conducted at Al-Azhar University. (Islamic University, Al-Azhar University)
4. **Time Limits:** This study was implemented in 2018 and therefore represents the reality at this time.

5. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

European foundation for quality management (EFQM)

The European model of excellence management is one of the most prominent models of excellence management used in the contemporary world, and the model is based on a fundamental principle of overall quality thought (Jad Al-Rab, 2013).

In 1988, fourteen heads of major European companies established the European Foundation for Quality Management (EFQM), with the aim of promoting excellence in performance and overall quality management in Europe and assisting its members in their efforts to implement TQM

and business excellence. In 1991, European Quality Organization (EQO) has established the European Quality Award (EQA) based on the framework of the European Foundation for Quality Management (EFQM) model. The European Model of Excellence is the first self-assessment model based on the overall quality of business results. T Ware model of the focus on the overall quality management model to focus on the excellence model (Porter and tanner, 2004).

The model was established by taking advantage of the advantages of the Malcolm model with the US National Scale, the Deming Award model, and the European Organization for Quality (EO) describes the European Excellence Model as a practical tool that helps the organization establish an appropriate management system by identifying its position towards excellence and helping it to understand gaps and then find solutions, The model reflects best practices (Antonaras et al., 2009).

The model allows for an understanding of the causes and impact relationships between the organizations' actions and the results achieved. The model is based on three integrated components (EFQM, 2013):

1. Basic concepts of excellence.
2. Standards of excellence.
3. Radar logic for evaluation.

Standards of Excellence:

In order to achieve sustainable success, organizations need strong leadership, a clear strategy, and need to develop and improve the workforce, partnerships and processes to deliver value added and services to beneficiaries. If applied, the right approach effectively, organizations will achieve what they and the beneficiaries expect. Therefore, the model was divided into nine criteria, including five possible, and four results as follows:

A. Possible (500 points):

1. Leadership: (100 points), distinguished organizations have leadership capable of shaping the future.
2. Policy and Strategy: (100 points), outstanding organizations implement their vision and mission through the development and implementation of a stakeholder focused strategy.
3. Individuals: (100 points), distinguished organizations appreciate their members and there is a culture that allows achieving both organizational goals and individual goals.
4. Partnership and resources: (100 points), outstanding organizations plan and manage relationships with external suppliers and with internal resources, to support policies, strategy and efficiency of operations.
5. Operations: (100 points). Distinguished organizations design, manage, and improve processes to create increased value for beneficiaries and other stakeholders.

B. Results (500 points):

1. Results of beneficiaries: (150 points), distinguished organizations achieve and maintain the desired results that meet the needs and expectations of beneficiaries.

2. Results of individuals: (100 points), distinguished organizations achieve and maintain the desired results that meet the needs of their individual and their expectations.
3. Community Outcomes: (100 points), distinguished organizations achieve and maintain the desired results

that meet the needs and expectations of stakeholders in society.

4. Key performance results: (150 points), outstanding organizations achieve and maintain the desired results that meet the needs and expectations of their stakeholders.

The following figure illustrates the criteria for excellence:

Figure 1: European Excellence Model EFQM

1. Standard focus on human resources:

Human Resources Management is the body that handles the most efficient use of human resources at all levels in the organization in order to contribute to achieving the goals (Al-Kutbi, 2005).

The University of Excellence manages the knowledge and potential of its employees and develops them at the individual level, the level of the work teams and the university level, and is interested in communication, reward and appreciation for its employees in a way that motivates them and develops their loyalty to use their skills and knowledge for the benefit of the University.

This criterion consists of the following sub-criteria:

1. Human resources planning, management and improvement through:
 - Develop human resources strategies, policies and plans (staff) at the university.
 - Engage staff in developing HR strategies, policies and plans.
 - Human resources policies and the organizational structure of the University are consistent with the University's policy and strategy.
2. To determine the continuity and development of knowledge and qualifications of human resources through:
 - Develop employee development and training plans, and use them to ensure that their capabilities meet the university's current and future needs.
 - Develop, train and train employees to help them realize their full potential.

- Help employees improve their performance through assessments and other activities.
- 3. Share and empower human resources through:
 - Enforce adequate staff powers and enable them to complete their work assignments.
 - Provide opportunities that stimulate interaction and support creativity and positive behavior of staff at all levels of the university.
 - Encourage employees to work with each other in teams in one field.
- 4. The reward, appreciation and attention to human resources at the university, through:
 - Assess individuals to encourage, empower and sustain their interaction.
 - Provide the University with appropriate levels of benefits (retirement, savings, and health insurance).
 - Provide resources and services that meet or exceed systems and labor laws for human resources development.

2. The impact of the emphasis on human resources on outstanding performance:

The human resources at the university are the most important resources at all, through the availability of a staff of education and research at the highest level, and a distinguished administrative staff that can provide the university educational and research services in the form required and achieve a competitive advantage of the University, and in this regard the University to manage the human resources in a suitable manner. (Scott & George, 2010) identifies human resources management as the process

of attracting, selecting, training, evaluating, and motivating human capital. Regis (2008) identifies human resources as: dealing with the daily requirements of Such as polarization, compensation, performance appraisal, and organizational development.

The recent trend in human resource management has been developed to play a comprehensive and strategic role in organizations, including universities. This new role is aimed at effectively managing and leading staff to contribute to the overall direction of the organization as well as to achieving the goals and objectives (Millmore et al., 2007).

Achieving outstanding performance results both at the level of human resources and at the level of the organization can be achieved only by the availability of distinct human forces that have the skills and abilities that help to achieve the continuous success of the organization and towards the outstanding performance through activating the human resource and its development and good management at various levels.

The real tool and effective force in achieving the goals and objectives of the organizations are the human resources of the highly skilled workers who are selected and the management provides them with opportunities for continuous development and training aimed at increasing their skills and increasing their intellectual and cognitive abilities in the development of performance. (Al-Salmi, 2002).

Therefore, there is a need for conditions that help university employees to develop their performance by working as a team, and taking risks to meet the needs and desires of beneficiaries and stakeholders. Human resources management should contribute to the creation of individuals to change towards excellence and continuous improvement, this approach in performance to the success of its implementation, and requires clear and intensive communication to explain the reasons for change and justification and the extent of its impact on workers.

El Talla et al. (2018) finds that the most important results of the impact of the emphasis on human resources on performance are as follows:

- Increase employee satisfaction and organizational loyalty.
- Improved individual and group performance at the university.
- The existence of a positive regulatory climate.
- Feeling employees of job security.
- The quality of dealing with students and beneficiaries and their needs quickly.
- Maintain university resources and rationalize consumption.
- Carry workers for their social responsibility.

3. Standard Operations:

Distinguished universities design, manage, and improve operations in order to support their policy and strategy, with

full satisfaction to create value for employees, students and other stakeholders (EFQM, 2013). This criterion consists of the following sub-criteria:

- A. Methodology for Process Design and Management, through:
 - Identify and design the necessary processes to implement the university policy and strategy and achieve its objectives.
 - The University's interest in completing the work according to the comprehensive quality systems and standard specifications.
 - Clearly define powers and responsibilities when performing operations.
- B. Improve processes in innovative ways to generate value for students and beneficiaries through:
 - Developing new processes, teaching methods, and new university management.
 - Encouraging the university to creatively innovate in the quality and diversity of services provided.
 - Stimulate innovative creative talents for employees, students and stakeholders to help with new improvements.
- C. Design academic programs and develop internal services according to students' needs through:
 - Use market research and student questionnaires to identify needs and perceptions of the current situation.
 - Design and develop new specialties as needed: students, beneficiaries and employers.
 - Predict the impact of modern technology on the development of new disciplines.
 - Use creativity and innovation to develop new learning styles and services.

4. Impact of Operations on Outstanding Performance:

One of the important principles of TQM is to focus on processes and not on results only. Hence, it is of great importance for universities to provide high quality and reliable operations that meet the needs of beneficiaries and stakeholders and elevate their performance to achieve excellence in performance. Examples include: Academic and administrative processes, scientific research and the use of learning and learning resources. These processes must be designed and implemented so as to reduce cost and effort on the one hand, and delay and risk on the other, while maximizing productivity, efficiency and quality of performance.

Operations are a set of activities that take one or more inputs and produce a way out for the beneficiary (Jad Al-Rab, 2009).

The organization is a "good and effective method of designing operations, based on preventing problems before they occur, and reviewing results to find ways to regulate procedures and reduce routine. It maintains two-way communication channels with customers to develop a precise

and growing understanding of their needs and expectations" (Al-Hayali, 2012).

Clients see the organization as an assessment of whether their operations serve their needs and respond to their desires easily and easily. The judgment is no longer confined to the outputs and results of the comprehensive corporate evaluation, as operations become focused on quality requirements (Al-Dajani, 2011).

Achieving the logic of operations management is clearly superior to the pattern of management and its achievements from traditional management. Performance is achieved through cohesion and interrelatedness in the organization's operations, thus improving the investment of resources and linking inputs to outputs on clear and measurable basis (Al-Salmi, 2002).

Al-Tala '(2016) believes that the most important results of the performance management impact on performance are as follows:

- Distinguished in university performance and in the results of internal and external evaluation.
- Evolution in teaching methods and administrative processes.
- The University achieves a financial surplus resulting from its operations.
- Increasing number of students enrolled in university.
- Increase the number of new programs adapted to the needs of the labor market.
- Higher opportunities for university graduates in employment compared to other universities.
- Reduce costs through the use of modern technology.
- Increase productivity and improve employee performance.

6. LITERATURE REVIEW

- Study of (Forrester, 2016), which aimed to explore the challenges faced by leaders in the implementation of programs of excellence in the work in the Jordanian public sector. The study adopted a content analysis methodology to analyze performance evaluation reports prepared by the King Abdullah II Center for Excellence, Public organizations participated in the King Abdullah II Award for Excellence more than once, and House reports that they failed to achieve satisfactory results. The results indicated that the main challenges affecting the implementation of public sector leadership standards in Jordan were the result of poor strategic planning, lack of staff empowerment, poor performance measurement, lack of financial resources, poor integration and coordination, and weak performance measurement system.
- Study of (Tichke et al., 2106), which aims to improve understanding of how to successfully disseminate performance excellence in organizations by comparing tools and strategies implemented by organizations at different levels of performance excellence. The survey used interviews, interviews and discussion groups to collect data from several countries: India, Japan, China, Singapore, and Thailand. The results indicated that on average, the most mature organizations in the application of excellence outperform the less mature organizations in the application, and that the more mature organizations in the application of excellence have a tendency to use specific tools effectively. The study also identified differences in the strategic approach to excellence among the more mature organizations and less mature in the application of excellence.
- Study of (Smulowitz, 2015) aimed at identifying the potential impact of performance indicators on the perceived outcome of organizational change to understand differences in stakeholder views. The data were collected by interviewing 32 participants from four departments to support educational services and a group of senior Leadership University. The results indicated that the two implementers failed to assess employee satisfaction, contribute to the implementation process, and performance indicators can be the main vision for successful change efforts.
- Study of (Moradzadeh, 2015), which aimed to identify the feasibility of applying the European model of excellence in higher education institutions. The descriptive method was used in the study. The data were collected from 22 educational zones through a random sample of (345), Middle, managers and staff, in all educational units. The results showed that the institutions of higher education under study applied well the elements of the European model of excellence, and that three main elements influencing the implementation of the criteria of the European model of excellence are the stakeholders, leadership and structure. The results also showed the need to develop a model that takes into account the local culture and other environmental factors and that standards of enterprise enable the results of beneficiaries, employee outcomes, community outcomes, and key performance outcomes.
- Study of (Al-Masri, 2014) which aimed to identify the role of smart leadership in mitigating the effects of work pressure. The researchers used the descriptive analytical method, and the questionnaire was used to collect data from the university leadership, which consists of (204) individuals. The results showed that there is a high level of smart leadership among university leaders, the existence of strategies to mitigate the effects of work pressures of managers at high level, and a relationship between smart leadership and the mitigation of the effects of work pressures, and that there are no differences in leadership level depending on the variables of the job title, while there are differences In leadership level depending on university variables, age, and experience.

- Study of (Al-Dajani, 2011), which aims to identify the role of strategic planning in the quality of institutional performance and the development of standards and indicators to measure the institutional performance in Palestinian universities. The researchers used the analytical descriptive approach and the constructive developmental approach. The study community consisted of deans, managers, Islamic University and Al-Aqsa University. The number of (100) members has been met (91) members (91%) of the society of the study. The study found that there were significant differences in the level of performance due to the university variable in favor of the Islamic University. The institutional performance rates in the Palestinian universities were high. The quality of performance in the dimensions of philosophy, mission, goals, governance and administration, institutional scope, institutional resources and services High, and showed a significant relationship between strategic planning and quality of institutional performance.
- Study of (Shirvani et al., 2011), which aimed at evaluating the performance of medical science universities based on the European model of excellence. This study was conducted between 2012 and 2011. The study was applied to a sample of 13 universities. The educational work of the nine standards of the model by a radar methodology through the managers who received the training. The results showed that all universities scored higher than 200/1000, while one university obtained 350/1000, and that the differences between the quality criteria and the performance results were between 19.4 and 102.5. The main performance results were higher and the results of the society the results indicated that there are no significant differences between the results and the possibilities and the nine criteria of the model according to the university variable. The study recommended that the Iranian medical universities plan and implement improvement projects for all standards, especially the results criteria.

7. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study followed the descriptive analytical method, in which it attempts to describe the phenomenon of the subject of the study, analyze its data, and explain the relationship between its components, the opinions that are raised around it, the processes it contains, and the effects that it causes.

The study population: The study population consists of all employees of supervisory positions in the public universities operating in Gaza Strip (Islamic University, Al-Azhar University) with 282 employees.

The study sample:

The sample of the study was selected using the stratified method of stratification as one of the statistical methods used to be representative of the study society according to the rules of scientific research in the selection of samples. The sample size was 135, which was determined according to the

rules for determining the sample size. The questionnaires were distributed manually, (119) of whom responded, by (88.1%). A sample of 29 individuals was selected from outside the study sample and statistical analysis was conducted on it to verify the validity and stability of the questionnaire.

Study tool:

To achieve the objective of the study, the questionnaire was used as a data collection tool, developed using the criteria set by the researchers, and to arrive at the questionnaire in its final form. It emerged in its final form, which consists of two main areas: In addition to the field of "operations" which are of (10) paragraphs.

Correction of Study Tool: The five-point Likert five-point scale was used to determine the importance of each paragraph of the questionnaire to measure respondents' responses to the questionnaire sections as follows:

Table 1: the degrees of the five-dimensional Likert scale

Category	Absolutely Agree	Agree	To Some Extent	Not Agree	Not Quite OK
Class	5	4	3	2	1

In addition, a numerical scale was used to give the mean of the arithmetical mean using the ordinal scale of significance. The study adopted the criterion mentioned by Abdel-Fattah (2008) to judge the trend when using the five-dimensional Likert scale.

Statistical Processes: The study used the Statistical Package of Social Sciences (SPSS) to perform the necessary analysis of the questionnaire data. The following statistical methods and tests were used: percentages, frequencies and arithmetic mean, Pearson Correlation Coefficient to measure the degree of correlation: This test examines the relationship between two variables and it was used to calculate the internal consistency and structural integrity of the questionnaire, the Cronbach's Alpha test to determine the persistence of the questionnaire, T test in the case of one T-Test: to determine whether the average response was neutral (60%) or more/less, and it has been used to confirm the mean significance of each paragraph of the questionnaire.

Validity of the study tool: The validity of the study tool has been verified using the constructional honesty method, which is a measure of the validity of the tool, which measures the extent to which the objectives of the tool are achieved, and shows the extent of the correlation of each field of study to the total score of the questionnaire. The correlation coefficients ranged between (0.949 - 0.955) and thus the scale is characterized by a high degree of honesty.

Stability of the study tool: The persistence of the study questionnaire was confirmed by the Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient. The following table shows that the value of the alpha-Cronbach coefficient was high for all domains, ranging from (0.914 to 0.922), which means that the questionnaire is stable.

Table 2: Determination of Determination of Determination of Determination by Cronbach's Alpha

No.	Dimension	No. Of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
1.	Standard focus on human resources	12	0.914
2.	Standard operations	10	0.922

Answer of the study questions:

In order to answer the study question, the researchers used several statistical methods, such as: arithmetical averages, standard deviations, as well as the use of a single sample T test for each of the domains. The answer of the paragraph is positive in the sense that the sample agrees with its content if the calculated t value is greater than the tabular t value of 1.99 or the probability value is less than 0.05 and the arithmetic mean of the paragraph is greater than (3). It is not in agreement with their content if the calculated t value is less than the tabular t value, which is 1.99, the probability value is greater than 0.05, the arithmetic mean of the paragraph is smaller than (3) and the views of the sample in the paragraph are neutral (moderately agreed) if the probability value is greater than (0.05).

Answer of the first question which states

Q1-: What is the availability of the focus on human resources in Palestinian public universities operating in the southern governorates?

In reviewing the responses of the sample of the study on the extent of adoption of the human resources focus criterion, Table 3 indicates that the arithmetic averages of all the areas of "planning, managing and developing human resources" ranged from (3.49 - 3.66). In general, (3.58)

The second area, "Identifying and Developing Continuity of Knowledge and Qualifications of Human Resources", ranged from 3.60 to 3.69. In general, this field obtained an arithmetic mean (3.66). The third field was "participation and empowerment of human resources" ranged between (3.50 - 3.78). In general, this field obtained an average of 3.67,

As for the fourth field, "the reward, appreciation and attention to human resources at the university", the averages for its paragraphs ranged from 3.60 to 4.26. In general, the field obtained an average of 3.83. Overall, the policy criterion and the strategy as a whole obtained an arithmetic average (3.68) which is a large.

The universities are concerned about their employees especially that these universities are the oldest universities in Gaza Strip and the most distinguished ones. These universities are public universities that apply the unified staff of universities in terms of salaries and incentives, and attract the best academic and administrative qualifications to work in them.

Table 3: Analysis of paragraphs and areas of focus on human resources

No.	Item / Dimension	Mean	S. D.	T – Test	Sig.	Rank
1.	Human resources strategies, policies and plans are developed at the university	3.57	0.83	7.43	0.00	2
2.	Employees are involved in the development of HR policies and strategies and their plans	3.49	0.85	6.25	0.00	3
3.	Human resources policies and the organizational structure of the University are consistent with the University's strategy	3.66	0.76	9.50	0.00	1
Planning, management and development of human resources		3.58	0.67	9.42	0.00	-
1.	Development and training plans for both years are developed and used to ensure that their capabilities meet the University's current and future needs	3.68	0.80	9.26	0.00	2
2.	Employees are developed, mentored and trained to help them realize their full potential	3.60	0.87	7.51	0.00	3
3.	Staff are assisted in improving their performance through assessments and other activities	3.69	0.91	8.19	0.00	1
Identify and develop the continuity of knowledge and qualifications of human resources		3.66	0.75	9.63	0.00	-
1.	Delegates are empowered and empowered to carry out their tasks	3.74	0.85	9.23	0.00	2
2.	Opportunities are provided that stimulate interaction and support creativity. There is positive behavior among staff at all levels of the university	3.50	0.77	7.03	0.00	3
3.	Employees are encouraged to work with each other within teams in one field	3.78	0.74	11.55	0.00	1
Participation and empowerment of human resources		3.67	0.65	11.25	0.00	-
1.	Individuals are appreciated for their encouragement, empowerment and continued interaction	3.60	0.95	6.85	0.00	3
2.	The University provides appropriate levels of benefits	4.26	0.79	17.49	0.00	1

No.	Item / Dimension	Mean	S. D.	T – Test	Sig.	Rank
	(retirement, savings, insurance)					
3.	Resources and services that meet human resources development systems are provided	3.62	0.79	8.57	0.00	2
	The reward, appreciation and attention to human resources at the university	3.83	0.60	15.04	0.00	-
	The focus on human resources as a whole	3.68	0.56	13.25	0.00	-

Answer to the second question which states

Q2-: What is the availability of the standard of operations in the Palestinian public universities operating in the southern governorates?

In reviewing the responses of the sample of the study on the extent to which the criterion of operations was adopted. Table 4 indicates that the mathematical averages for all areas of the "Process Design and Management Methodology" ranged from 3.71 to 3.85. In general, the second area, "Improving processes in innovative ways to generate added value for students and beneficiaries" ranged from 3.58 to 3.82, the field has an average of 3.72. The third area is "Design and development of academic programs and internal services as per students", the arithmetic averages ranged

from 3.50 to 3.77, and there was a difference in this area with arithmetic average (3.69), and in general, the standard of operations as a whole has obtained an arithmetic average (3.73), which is large.

The researchers attributed this to the fact that the universities, in terms of their commitment to competitiveness and quality in their operations, adapt their operations to the requirements of the National Commission for Accreditation and Quality, as well as seeking certificates and awards of international excellence that improve their position in the global rankings of universities, and does not open any new programs except after obtaining the necessary accreditation from the National Authority for Accreditation and Quality in the Ministry of Education and Higher Education.

Table 4: Analysis of paragraphs and areas of operations

No.	Item / Dimension	Mean	S. D.	T – Test	Sig.	Rank
1.	The necessary processes are identified and designed to implement the university policy and strategy and achieve its objectives	3.71	0.69	11.11	0.00	3
2.	The Corporation is concerned with the completion of works according to the comprehensive quality systems and standard specifications	3.82	0.76	11.90	0.00	2
3.	The powers and responsibilities are clearly defined upon completion of operations	3.85	0.77	12.08	0.00	1
	Methodology of Process Design and Management	3.79	0.62	13.92	0.00	-
1.	New processes, teaching methods, and university management are being developed and implemented	3.82	0.74	12.08	0.00	1
2.	The University encourages creative creativity in the quality and diversity of services provided	3.75	0.82	10.01	0.00	2
3.	Innovative creative talents are mobilized for employees, students and stakeholders to help with new improvements	3.58	0.90	7.05	0.00	3
	Improve processes in innovative ways to generate value for students and beneficiaries	3.72	0.71	11.02	0.00	-
1.	Market research and student questionnaires are used to identify needs and perceptions of the current situation	3.50	0.82	6.58	0.00	4
2.	New specialties are designed and developed as needed: students, beneficiaries, and employers	3.77	0.81	10.45	0.00	1
3.	The impact of modern technology on the development of new disciplines is expected	3.76	0.65	12.68	0.00	2
4.	Creativity and innovation are used to develop new learning styles and services	3.72	0.80	9.83	0.00	3
	Designing and developing academic programs and internal services according to students' needs	3.69	0.63	11.89	0.00	-
	Standard operations as a whole	3.73	0.58	13.57	0.00	-

8. RESULTS

The study reached a number of results, the most important of which were:

- There is a high level of achievement of the criterion of focus on human resources with a percentage (73.6%)
- The following are the sub-areas of the Human Resources focus: (reward, appreciation and attention to human resources at the university, participation and empowerment of human resources, identification and development of the continuity of knowledge and qualifications of human resources, and finally: planning, management and development of human resources).
- There is a high level of emphasis on operations and a percentage of 74.6%
- The sub-areas of the Process Focus Standard are: Process Design and Management Methodology, Innovative Process Improvement to Generate Value for Students and Beneficiaries, Design and Development of Academic Programs and Internal Services as Students Need.

9. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the above results, the study recommended:

- Make more effort in the planning, management and development of human resources in universities.
- To identify and develop the continuity of knowledge and qualifications of human resources through training courses and scholarships for members of the academic body.
- To increase the participation and empowerment of human resources in decision-making.
- The reward, appreciation and attention to human resources at the university through the implementation of amendments to the unified staff of universities.
- Work on the design and development of academic programs and internal services according to the needs of students and to meet the labor market.
- Improve processes in innovative ways to generate value for students and beneficiaries.

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